

ABSTRACT BOOK

#EHMA2022

EHMA 2022

**FROM PEOPLE TO SYSTEMS:
LEADERSHIP FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE**

**15-17 June 2022
Brussels, Belgium**

The EHMA 2022 Annual Conference

EHMA 2022 is the 27th Annual Conference of the European Health Management Association taking place in conjunction with the association's 40th anniversary. It brings together key healthcare stakeholders providing the latest evidence to guide the much-needed transformation of health systems. It supports managers and health systems to excel at a time where the complexity of the challenge ahead is immense.

The 2022 conference theme '*From people to systems: leadership for a sustainable future*' explores challenges and solutions to creating sustainable health systems and ways health managers can lead towards them.

One of EHMA's main areas of work has been maintaining a dialogue between policymakers, health managers and professionals, thereby facilitating policy refinement and change. The EHMA 2022 Annual Conference is an occasion for health managers and professionals to have their voices heard, to connect with decision-makers, and inform policymaking at the European level.

Every year, the EHMA Annual Conference attracts research from leading universities, creating space to exchange knowledge on excellent delivery of healthcare and showcase evidence-based practices at the country, systems and organisational level. The conference is abstract-driven and features research by leading experts on the most contemporary topics on health management. It is a place for all healthcare stakeholders to come together to exchange innovation and best practices.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

171 - Patient experiences library

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Abstract

Patients trust doctors with their health. But how doctors communicate with the patients and how patients feel when at the “doctors office” impacts the patient journey in different ways. With our ongoing project, we are aiming to provide platform of a video library of stories and experiences in the “doctors’ office”, designed to empower both patients and health professionals and to enable experience-based knowledge.

Method

As a first step towards developing the video library, we asked individuals on Social Media to share 3 words when thinking about their medical consultation. Based on the social media campaign, we developed a set of questions as an interview guide for interviews.

Results

The Social Media campaign provided us insights into the feelings of patients when being at the doctors office. The common words about how people across the world feel when visiting a doctor can be summarised into confused, frustrated, no shown empathy, anxious and intimidated. But also heard, relieved, supported.

Conclusion

The interactive library will allow patients from across the globe to search for interviews based on what their peers have been experiencing at that time, exploring stories and lessons shared by someone who has been in a similar situation. This will bring experience based learning and empowering the patients via other patient stories.

